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NAVIGATING THE NEXUS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF BIOPHARMACEUTICS AND PHARMACOKINETICS IN UNRAVELLING THE COMPLEXITIES OF DRUG ABSORPTION.

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ABSTRACT

In the labyrinthine realm of drug development, the symbiotic disciplines of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics emerge as indispensable navigators, steering the course from formulation to therapeutic efficacy. This comprehensive review intricately weaves through the multifaceted landscape of drug absorption, unravelling the synergistic dance between these pivotal realms. From decoding drug formulation intricacies to exploring the dynamic interplay between drugs and physiological systems, this article immerses the reader in the cellular ballet of absorption mechanisms. With a spotlight on influential factors and pioneering delivery systems, the narrative extends to the integration of in vitro and in vivo models, ultimately culminating in a forward-looking examination of challenges and future trajectories. "Navigating the Nexus" serves as a guiding beacon, inviting researchers and practitioners to embark on a captivating journey through the complexities of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics, shedding light on the nexus where drug development meets scientific innovation.

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INTRODUCTION

The realm of drug development is akin to an intricate labyrinth, where success hinges on the ability to navigate the complex interplay of scientific disciplines. At the heart of this labyrinth lies the dynamic duo of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics—disciplines that serve as the compass and map, guiding researchers through the intricate journey from drug formulation to therapeutic efficacy. In this comprehensive review, we embark on an expedition to unravel the mysteries surrounding drug absorption, exploring the symbiotic relationship between these two pillars of pharmaceutical science. As pharmaceutical landscapes evolve, the imperative to understand the complexities of drug absorption becomes ever more pressing. The effectiveness of a drug, regardless of its ingenuity, is intrinsically linked to its journey through the human body. Biopharmaceutics, the art and science of drug formulation, dictates how a drug is prepared for its odyssey, while pharmacokinetics elucidates the pharmacological fate of the drug within the body—a dynamic process governed by a series of intricate dance steps between the drug and the physiological systems. The synergy between biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics is akin to navigating a nexus—a convergence points where the intricacies of drug formulation meet the dynamic physiological responses that shape a drug's destiny. This nexus is not a static crossroads but a dynamic interplay influenced by an orchestra of variables, from the molecular characteristics of the drug to the physiological nuances of the human body. In this review, we embark on a journey through the corridors of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics, peeling back the layers of complexity that shroud drug absorption. From the solid-state intricacies of drug formulation to the cellular ballet at the mucosal interface, we delve into the science that underpins the absorption process. Along the way, we encounter factors that influence drug absorption—variables that orchestrate a symphony of complexities, challenging researchers to predict and optimize drug performance in diverse biological contexts.

As we navigate this intellectual terrain, we also explore the frontier of advanced drug delivery systems—technological marvels that hold the promise of revolutionizing how drugs traverse the body. Nanoparticles, liposomes, and microneedle arrays emerge as pioneers in this landscape, offering a glimpse into a future where precision and targeted drug delivery are paramount. [1]

Biopharmaceutics: Decoding Drug Formulation:

At the inception of a drug's journey from bench to bedside, the science of biopharmaceutics stands as the cornerstone, orchestrating the intricate symphony of drug formulation. This section unveils the complexities inherent in the art and science of preparing pharmaceuticals for their therapeutic voyage, exploring the fundamental principles that govern drug formulation and set the stage for the subsequent pharmacokinetic dance within the human body.

Solid-State Considerations:

The foundation of drug formulation lies in the solid-state characteristics of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API). This subsection delves into the molecular intricacies, polymorphism, and crystallinity of the drug, unravelling how these solid-state properties influence drug stability, solubility, and ultimately, bioavailability. The ability to decode and manipulate the solid-state nature of a drug is crucial in sculpting its performance in various dosage forms.

Dissolution Dynamics:

As a drug journeys through the gastrointestinal tract, its fate is intimately tied to its ability to dissolve and be absorbed. This section explores the dissolution dynamics of drugs, examining the interplay between physicochemical properties, dosage form characteristics, and the physiological environment. From the nuances of dissolution testing to the impact of formulation variables, we illuminate the factors that govern a drug's liberation from its dosage form—a pivotal step in the absorption narrative.

Dosage Form Design:

The canvas upon which the art of biopharmaceutics is painted is the dosage form. Tablets, capsules, liquids, and more—each represents a carefully crafted vehicle for drug delivery. Here, we unravel the design principles behind various dosage forms, addressing the role of excipients, fillers, binders, and coatings in shaping drug release profiles. The section also explores innovations in dosage form design, such as multi-particulate systems and controlled-release formulations, highlighting how these advancements contribute to the optimization of drug absorption.

Pharmacokinetics: A Dance with the Body:

In the symphony of drug development, pharmacokinetics takes centre stage as the choreographer, orchestrating a delicate dance between the administered drug and the intricate physiological ballet within the human body. This section delves into the nuanced steps of this dance, unravelling the dynamic processes that govern the fate of a drug from absorption to excretion.

Absorption: The Opening Act

The dance begins with absorption—a pivotal act that determines how a drug crosses the barriers into systemic circulation. This subsection explores the diverse mechanisms through which drugs navigate the mucosal interface, from passive diffusion to active transport. The cellular ballet unfolds as drugs traverse biological membranes, encountering challenges such as variable pH environments and complex transport systems.

Understanding the intricacies of drug absorption involves unravelling the kinetics of absorption—examining not only how quickly a drug enters the bloodstream but also the extent of its absorption. Concepts such as bioavailability and first-pass metabolism come to the forefront, shaping the narrative of a drug's journey through the body. [2]

Distribution: Waltzing through the Circulatory System

Once absorbed, the drug embarks on a waltz through the circulatory system, reaching its destination in various tissues. This section explores the factors influencing drug distribution, from blood flow patterns to tissue permeability. The dance of drug-protein binding is unveiled, with an emphasis on how bound and unbound fractions influence the pharmacological activity and elimination of the drug.

Intriguingly, the blood-brain barrier emerges as a formidable partner in this dance, influencing the accessibility of drugs to the central nervous system. The dynamic equilibrium between plasma and tissue concentrations paints a nuanced picture of drug distribution, underscoring the need for a comprehensive understanding of these pharmacokinetic intricacies.

Metabolism: Choreographing Transformation

The metabolic phase of drug pharmacokinetics represents a transformative choreography—a biochemical dance where drugs undergo enzymatic conversions, primarily in the liver. This subsection delves into the role of cytochrome P450 enzymes and other metabolic pathways, illuminating how drug metabolism can give rise to active metabolites or render the drug inert.

Beyond the liver, extrahepatic metabolism performs its own dance, adding another layer of complexity to the pharmacokinetic narrative. The interplay of genetic factors and environmental influences on drug metabolism is explored, emphasizing the personalized nature of this aspect of pharmacokinetics.

Excretion: The Grand Finale

The pharmacokinetic dance concludes with excretion—a grand finale where the body bids farewell to the drug and its metabolites. Renal excretion takes the spotlight, showcasing the role of glomerular filtration, tubular secretion, and reabsorption in shaping the drug's elimination profile. Hepatic and biliary excretion also contribute their unique moves to this final act.

Factors influencing drug excretion, such as renal impairment and age-related changes, are explored in this section. The importance of clearance concepts and half-life calculations provides a rhythmic closure to the pharmacokinetic journey, bringing the dance to a harmonious end.

Therapeutic Drug Monitoring: The Maestro's Baton

Therapeutic drug monitoring emerges as the maestro's baton, guiding clinicians in fine-tuning drug regimens based on individual patient responses. This subsection discusses the significance of monitoring drug concentrations in ensuring optimal therapeutic outcomes, considering the dynamic nature of pharmacokinetics among diverse patient populations.[3]

Mechanisms of Drug Absorption: A Cellular Ballet:

In the intricate dance of drug absorption, cells take centre stage, orchestrating a finely tuned ballet that determines the fate of therapeutic agents within the body. This section unveils the choreography of this cellular ballet, elucidating the diverse mechanisms by which drugs traverse biological membranes and permeate the cellular barriers that guard entry into systemic circulation.

Passive Diffusion: The Graceful Glide Across Membranes

Passive diffusion, akin to a graceful glide, stands as the fundamental balletic movement in drug absorption. Small, lipophilic molecules traverse cell membranes effortlessly, driven by concentration gradients. This section explores the physicochemical factors influencing passive diffusion, from molecular size and lipophilicity to the role of ionization, providing insights into the elegant simplicity that underlies the most basic form of drug absorption.

Active Transport: Energetic Leaps of Cellular Engagement

In contrast to passive diffusion, active transport introduces energetic leaps into the cellular ballet. Membrane proteins, such as transporters, engage in intricate choreography to ferry specific drugs against concentration gradients. This segment dissects the various active transport mechanisms, including primary and secondary active transport, shedding light on how cellular machinery orchestrates the selective and energy-dependent movement of drugs across membranes.

Facilitated Diffusion: Partnered Movements in Molecular Symphony

Facilitated diffusion adds a collaborative layer to the cellular ballet, as carrier proteins assist in the movement of certain molecules across membranes. This section explores the partnership between drugs and carrier proteins, unravelling the nuances of facilitated diffusion and its significance in drug absorption, particularly for larger or polar molecules that face challenges with passive diffusion.

Transcytosis: Crossing Cellular Barriers with Elegance

In the grandeur of drug absorption, transcytosis emerges as an elegant manoeuvre, allowing drugs to traverse cellular barriers intact. This section unveils the cellular mechanisms involved in transcytosis, including vesicular transport and endocytosis, offering a glimpse into how macromolecules and nanoparticles navigate the cellular landscape with finesse.

Paracellular Transport: Treading the Tightrope Between Cells

The cellular ballet extends to the tightrope walk of paracellular transport, where drugs navigate the spaces between cells. This segment delves into the factors influencing paracellular transport, such as tight junctions and the permeability of the intercellular spaces, providing an understanding of how drugs delicately tread this tightrope to enter the bloodstream.

Cellular Barriers: Guardians of Systemic Entry

To comprehend the cellular ballet fully, one must appreciate the guardians—the cellular barriers that regulate drug entry. From the epithelial cells of the gastrointestinal tract to the endothelial cells of blood vessels, this section explores the role of various cellular barriers in shaping the absorption profiles of drugs and influencing their pharmacokinetics.[4]

Factors Influencing Drug Absorption: The Symphony of Variables:

In the intricate orchestration of drug absorption, a symphony of variables converges to dictate the fate of a therapeutic agent within the human body. This section elucidates the myriad factors that form the harmonic composition of this symphony, influencing how drugs traverse the biological landscapes and emphasizing the need for a nuanced understanding in the realm of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics.

Physiological Variables: Tuning the Environment

- **Gastrointestinal pH:** The pH gradient along the gastrointestinal tract plays a pivotal role in drug absorption. This subsection explores how variations in pH impact the ionization state of drugs, affecting their solubility and permeability. From the acidic realms of the stomach to the more neutral environment of the small intestine, the pH landscape sets the stage for the initial movements in this symphony.
- **Surface Area and Blood Flow:** The surface area available for drug absorption and the blood flow to the absorption site are fundamental determinants. We delve into the importance of these variables in governing the rate and extent of absorption, emphasizing their role in orchestrating the harmonious interaction between drugs and the absorptive surfaces.
- **Gastrointestinal Motility:** The rhythmic contractions of the gastrointestinal tract influence the time a drug spends in contact with absorptive surfaces. This subsection explores the impact of gastrointestinal motility on drug absorption kinetics, shedding light on how variations in motility patterns can alter the absorption profile of different drugs.

Formulation-Related Variables: Crafting the Melody

- **Dosage Form:** The design of the drug formulation sets the tone for drug absorption. This section investigates how the choice between tablets, capsules, and other formulations influences dissolution rates, disintegration times, and ultimately, the bioavailability of the drug.
- **Excipients:** The inclusion of excipients in drug formulations is akin to selecting instruments for a musical ensemble. We unravel the role of excipients in modulating drug solubility, stability, and permeability, highlighting their contribution to the overall performance of the drug in the absorption symphony.
- **Particle Size and Polymorphism:** Exploring the solid-state intricacies of drug formulations, we delve into how particle size and polymorphic forms impact dissolution and, consequently, absorption. The subtle nuances of crystal structures and particle morphology become instrumental in shaping the absorption profile.

Patient-Related Variables: Personalizing the Composition

- **Genetic Factors:** The genomic composition of individuals introduces a unique melody into the symphony of drug absorption. We explore the influence of genetic polymorphisms in drug-metabolizing enzymes and transporters, emphasizing the emerging field of pharmacogenomics in tailoring drug therapy based on individual genetic profiles.
- **Age, Gender, and Ethnicity:** The age, gender, and ethnicity of patients contribute additional layers to the symphony. From age-related changes in gastrointestinal physiology to gender disparities in drug absorption, we unravel the intricate interplay of demographic factors that influence the personalized performance of the drug absorption symphony.
- **Disease States:** Disease-induced alterations in physiological parameters can drastically alter drug absorption. This subsection navigates through the complexities of drug absorption in various disease states, highlighting the need for tailored therapeutic approaches in the context of altered physiological conditions.[5]

Advanced Drug Delivery Systems: Pioneering Precision:

In the ever-evolving landscape of pharmaceutical sciences, the chapter of drug delivery systems stands as a testament to human ingenuity. This section of our comprehensive review illuminates the pioneering strides made in advanced drug delivery systems, showcasing how these innovations are transforming the precision and efficacy of drug absorption.

Nanoparticles: Orchestrating Targeted Delivery

At the forefront of advanced drug delivery, nanoparticles emerge as veritable maestros orchestrating the symphony of targeted delivery. Engineered at the nanoscale, these carriers navigate physiological barriers with finesse, capitalizing on enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effects. From liposomes to polymeric nanoparticles, this sub-section dissects the diverse arsenal of nanoparticles, exploring how they encapsulate therapeutic agents and navigate biological terrains, enabling precise drug delivery to specific tissues and cells.

Liposomes: Cellular Harmony in Drug Delivery

Liposomes, phospholipid-based vesicles, take centre stage as carriers that resonate with the body's cellular harmony. In this segment, we delve into the biocompatible nature of liposomes and their ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs. Their amphiphilic structure allows for seamless integration into cell membranes, facilitating controlled drug release and minimizing systemic toxicity. The review explores the applications of liposomes in delivering a diverse range of therapeutic agents, from conventional drugs to nucleic acids.

Microneedle Arrays: Bridging the Transdermal Divide

Breaking the barriers of traditional drug delivery, microneedle arrays emerge as innovative tools in bridging the transdermal divide. This section investigates how these micron-sized needles traverse the stratum corneum, providing a minimally invasive yet highly effective route for drug delivery. From enhancing the permeability of skin barriers to enabling the painless administration of therapeutic compounds, microneedle arrays exemplify precision in drug delivery, offering a promising avenue for systemic and localized absorption.

Implantable Drug Delivery Systems: Sustaining Therapeutic Symphony

In the realm of sustained drug release, implantable drug delivery systems play a pivotal role in maintaining the therapeutic symphony over extended durations. This portion explores the design principles behind implantable devices, such as drug-eluting implants and osmotic pumps. By providing a controlled and sustained release of therapeutic agents, these systems contribute to minimizing fluctuations in drug concentrations, optimizing efficacy, and reducing side effects.

Challenges and Future Perspectives: Harmonizing Precision

While advanced drug delivery systems offer unparalleled precision, challenges persist. This section addresses obstacles such as biocompatibility, scalability, and regulatory considerations. Furthermore, we peer into the future, envisioning the integration of smart drug delivery systems guided by real-time monitoring and feedback mechanisms, paving the way for a new era of precision medicine.

In Vitro and In Vivo Models: Bridging the Gap:

The synergy between in vitro and in vivo models plays a pivotal role in unravelling the complexities of drug absorption. These models, serving as indispensable tools, form a dynamic bridge that spans the gap between controlled laboratory settings and the intricacies of living organisms. As we embark on this exploration, we delve into the significance, challenges, and evolving applications of in vitro and in vivo models, recognizing their synergistic role in advancing our understanding of drug absorption.

In Vitro Models: Crafting Precision in Controlled Environments

In vitro models serve as the artisans' workshop, providing a controlled environment where specific aspects of drug absorption can be meticulously examined. From cell cultures that replicate physiological barriers to artificial membrane systems that simulate permeability, in vitro models offer a high degree of precision and reproducibility. Researchers can manipulate variables with surgical precision, studying drug behaviour in isolation from the complex milieu of a living organism.

- **Cell Cultures and Permeability Assays:** Cellular models, ranging from Caco-2 cells to primary cell cultures, mimic the physiological barriers encountered during drug absorption. Permeability assays, such as the parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA), allow researchers to gauge a drug's ability to traverse membranes, providing valuable insights into absorption potential.
- **Precision in Formulation Studies:** In vitro models excel in elucidating the behaviour of drug formulations. Dissolution testing, for instance, enables researchers to predict how a drug will dissolve and become bioavailable in the gastrointestinal tract. This precision aids in optimizing formulation strategies for enhanced absorption.

In Vivo Models: Navigating the Complex Realities of Living Organisms

While in vitro models offer precision, in vivo models navigate the intricate and dynamic realities of living organisms. Animal models and human clinical trials provide a holistic understanding of how drugs interact with the entire physiological system. These models capture the essence of absorption in a living organism, accounting for complexities such as metabolism, distribution, and systemic responses.

- **Animal Models:** Rodents, rabbits, and larger mammals serve as surrogates for human physiology in preclinical studies. These models allow researchers to observe how a drug behaves in a living system, offering insights into absorption kinetics, bioavailability, and potential adverse effects.
- **Human Clinical Trials:** The pinnacle of in vivo research, clinical trials provide a real-world assessment of drug absorption in human subjects. These trials, conducted in phases, allow researchers to validate findings from preclinical studies, assess safety, and gather critical data on pharmacokinetics in diverse patient populations.

Bridging the Gap: Integrating In Vitro and In Vivo Insights

The true power of understanding drug absorption lies in the synergy between in vitro and in vivo models. While in vitro studies offer precision and early insights, in vivo models provide a contextual understanding within the complexity of living organisms. The bridge between these realms allows for a comprehensive assessment of drug behaviour, enabling researchers to refine predictions, validate hypotheses, and make informed decisions in the drug development process.

- **Translational Challenges:** Bridging the gap between in vitro and in vivo findings comes with challenges. Translating results from cell cultures to living organisms requires a nuanced understanding of the limitations and potential disparities. Researchers must navigate issues such as species differences, cellular context, and the dynamic nature of biological systems.
- **Quantitative Systems Pharmacology (QSP):** Emerging as a powerful approach, QSP integrates in vitro and in vivo data into computational models. These models simulate the intricate dynamics of drug absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion, facilitating a more accurate prediction of drug behaviour in humans.[6]

Challenges and Future Directions: Navigating Uncharted Waters:

It is imperative to acknowledge and address the challenges that currently cast shadows over the landscape of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics. Simultaneously, we must chart a course towards uncharted waters, where the future promises transformative breakthroughs.

Current Challenges:

1. **Inter-Individual Variability:** The mosaic of inter-individual variability stands as a formidable challenge in drug development. Genetic polymorphisms, variations in age, and the coexistence of diverse comorbidities contribute to a spectrum of individual responses to drug absorption. Navigating this intricate landscape requires a paradigm shift toward personalized medicine—an approach that tailors drug formulations and dosages to the unique characteristics of each patient.
2. **Transporter Interactions:** The recognition of the pivotal role played by transporters in drug absorption has brought forth a new layer of complexity. The dynamic interplay between drugs and transporters, coupled with modulation by endogenous compounds, adds a level of intricacy that demands a deeper understanding. The challenge lies in deciphering these intricate interactions to predict and optimize drug transport across biological membranes, emphasizing the need for innovative strategies in drug design and development.
3. **Biorelevant Models:** The translational gap between in vitro and in vivo models remains a challenge. While in vitro models offer controlled environments for experimentation, their ability to faithfully replicate the complexity of in vivo drug absorption is limited. Bridging this gap requires the development of more biorelevant models that accurately mimic the physiological conditions of the human body, allowing for more reliable predictions of drug behaviour and efficacy.

Future Directions:

1. **Personalized Medicine and Pharmacogenomics:** The future of drug absorption lies in the realm of personalized medicine. Advances in pharmacogenomics hold the promise of tailoring drug therapies to an individual's genetic makeup. Understanding the genetic factors influencing drug absorption will pave the way for precision medicine, optimizing treatment outcomes and minimizing adverse effects.
2. **Integration of Systems Biology:** Embracing the complexity of biological systems through systems biology approaches offers a holistic understanding of drug absorption. Integrating data from genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics can provide a comprehensive view of the molecular mechanisms governing drug interactions within the body, enabling the design of more effective and targeted therapies.
3. **Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning:** The application of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms holds great promise in predicting and optimizing drug absorption. Harnessing the power of big data, these technologies can analyse complex datasets, identify patterns, and predict individualized drug responses. This synergy between computational approaches and experimental data can revolutionize drug development processes.
4. **Innovations in Drug Delivery Systems:** Future drug absorption will be shaped by innovations in drug delivery systems. Smart drug delivery technologies, such as stimuli-responsive nanoparticles and targeted drug carriers, aim to enhance drug absorption at specific sites within the body. These advancements hold the potential to improve therapeutic efficacy while minimizing side effects.

CONCLUSION

In the intricate tapestry of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics, this comprehensive review sought to illuminate the path forward, providing a compass for researchers and practitioners navigating the complexities of drug absorption. As we reflect on the journey through the nexus of drug development, several key insights emerge, guiding us toward an era of enhanced understanding and innovation.

Unveiling the Layers of Complexity: Our exploration began with the fundamental principles of biopharmaceutics, dissecting the intricate dance between drug formulation and its physicochemical properties. Through the lens of pharmacokinetics, we unravelled the pharmacological fate of drugs within the dynamic landscape of the human body. The cellular ballet of drug absorption revealed itself, showcasing the multifaceted mechanisms at play, from passive diffusion to active transport.

Orchestrating a Symphony of Variables: The absorption of drugs is a symphony where countless variables harmonize and clash. From the influence of physiological factors to the delicate formulation nuances, this review underscored the complexity of predicting and optimizing drug absorption. Each factor contributes to the unique melody that dictates a drug's journey through the intricate pathways of the body.

Pioneering Precision in Drug Delivery: The landscape of drug delivery systems emerged as a frontier of innovation, with nanoparticles, liposomes, and microneedle arrays at the vanguard. These advancements promise not only improved therapeutic outcomes but also a paradigm shift in how we envision drug delivery, moving from conventional approaches to precision-based strategies.

Bridging the Gap between Models: In our exploration, we traversed the bridge between in vitro and in vivo models, recognizing the complementary roles they play in unravelling the mysteries of drug absorption. As technologies evolve, the synergy between these models becomes increasingly vital, offering a more holistic understanding of drug behaviour from bench to bedside.

Navigating Challenges, Charting the Future: As we confronted current challenges—inter-individual variability, transporter interactions, and the quest for biorelevant models—we acknowledged the complexity inherent in drug development. These challenges, however, are not roadblocks but rather catalysts for innovation. The promise of personalized medicine, the integration of genomics, and the application of artificial intelligence are beacons lighting the way toward a future where drug absorption is finely tailored to individual needs.

A Call to Action: In conclusion, our journey through the nexus of biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics is not a conclusion but a call to action. The complexities unveiled herein are invitations for researchers, clinicians, and pharmaceutical visionaries to embark on a journey of discovery, pushing the boundaries of knowledge and reshaping the landscape of drug absorption. As we navigate the uncharted waters ahead, armed with newfound insights and technologies, the promise of more effective and personalized therapeutic interventions beckons—a testament to the endless possibilities when science, innovation, and a deep understanding of the nexus converge.

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REFERENCES

1. Wu D, Sanghavi M, Kollipara S, Ahmed T, Saini AK, Heimbach T. Physiologically based pharmacokinetics modelling in biopharmaceutics: case studies for establishing the bioequivalence safe space for innovator and generic drugs. *Pharmaceutical Research*. 2023 Feb;40(2):337-57.
2. Ogihara T, Mizoi K, Ishii-Watabe A. Pharmacokinetics of Biopharmaceuticals: Their Critical Role in Molecular Design. *Biomedicines*. 2023 May 16;11(5):1456.
3. Zhang Q, Han Y, Xiang H, Li M, Yang L, Liu Q, Zhang Y, Zhang Z, Lin Q, Zhang L. Biopharmaceutical, preclinical pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic investigations of an orally administered novel 3-nbutylphthalide prodrug for ischemic stroke treatment. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023 Jan 1;180:106308.
4. Wu D, Li M. Current state and challenges of physiologically based biopharmaceutics modeling (PBBM) in oral drug product development. *Pharmaceutical Research*. 2023 Feb;40(2):321-36.
5. Krstevska A, Đuriš J, Ibrić S, Cvijić S. A text mining study on the utility of physiologically based pharmacokinetic/biopharmaceutics modeling (PBPK/PBBM) in formulation development. *Macedonian Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2023;69(Suppl 1):145-6.
6. Rebelato ER, Rauber GS, Caon T. An update of nano-based drug delivery systems for cannabinoids: Biopharmaceutical aspects & therapeutic applications. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2023 Feb 15:122727.

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